

THE ROLE OF THE “HUJUM” MOVEMENT IN ENSURING
WOMEN'S EQUALITY IN THE UZBEK SSR

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Abstract. This article attempts to reveal the causes, outcomes, and consequences of the “Hujum” movement, a campaign aimed at unveiling women in the Uzbek SSR during the 1920s and 1930s. The author examines the historical background of the campaign, its implementation, and its impact on the social status of women in Central Asia.

Keywords: Central Asia, Hujum, paranja, women, Islam, society, Bolsheviks, social processes, cooperation.

Anyone with a basic knowledge of history knows that great social revolutions cannot be accomplished without the active participation of women. Since the Communists in Central Asia sought to transform people’s consciousness and way of life, they primarily aimed to weaken the influence of Islam and bring women into public life. To achieve this goal, religion was declared a harmful belief system. In their view, the citizens of a communist society were expected to adopt “communist atheism” as their worldview. At the same time, various measures were introduced to eliminate the paranja, the traditional outer garment worn by Central Asian women. The campaign against women’s veiling became known as the “Hujum” movement [1].

During the first years of Soviet rule, several legal acts were adopted in Turkestan aimed at the “liberation” of indigenous women. These laws established formal equality between men and women, prohibited polygamy, bride price payments, and forced marriages involving underage girls [2]. Decrees such as

“Equal Pay for Equal Work for Women and Men” and “On the Protection of Motherhood and Childhood” were also enacted.

Following the decree abolishing the bride price in 1924, the wives of Uzbek workers became the first group to remove the paranja. On March 8, 1927, Isaac Abramovich Zelensky, the First Secretary of the Central Asian Bureau of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks), organized the first large-scale public unveiling event in Registan Square in Samarkand. Women who had agreed to remove their paranjas were brought from different regions of the country and participated alongside activists who had already joined the movement.

On that day, approximately 10,000 women removed their paranjas. Within the following three months, another 90,000 women followed their example. However, this event provoked strong resistance within society, especially among men. Family conflicts increased, and public dissatisfaction became widespread. Several women who removed their veils were killed by relatives. Among the first victims were Surmakhon Shermatova and the young actress Nurkhon Yuldashkhojayeva.

It should be emphasized that the first propaganda efforts related to the “Hujum” campaign had already begun in 1924. However, these initial attempts were unsuccessful because the majority of women in Central Asia had been raised within a deeply religious environment. Wearing the paranja was closely associated with traditional interpretations of Islamic requirements regarding female modesty and public appearance.

At the same time, the campaign represented an unprecedented attempt to transform social relations. The proclamation of “gender equality,” “equal pay for equal work,” and “equal opportunities in social and political activities,” which were reflected in Soviet legislation (though not always fully realized in practice), was a significant development not only for society but also for women themselves [3].

Women continued to wear the paranja in remote rural areas until the 1940s and, in some places, even into the 1950s. While the mass disappearance of the

paranja occurred during the years of the Second World War, its complete disappearance was largely achieved by the 1950s.

According to Soviet ideology, genuine equality between men and women could only be achieved when women were freed from domestic servitude and actively involved in public life. The Communist Party sought to integrate women into social production based on the Marxist-Leninist theory that collective labor played a decisive role in shaping human consciousness. Through participation in social labor, women were expected to gain independence within both the family and society, develop their creative potential, and contribute to the formation of a new social order that would transcend traditional kinship-based structures [4].

The abandonment of the paranja had contradictory consequences. On the one hand, it facilitated women's participation in public life, increased their social activity, and improved their social status. On the other hand, it also created opportunities for their exploitation as a source of inexpensive labor. As a result of the campaign, the Soviet state gained access to millions of female workers whose labor was utilized particularly intensively during the Second World War.

During the "Hujum" campaign, women began to be recruited into industrial production, especially in the silk, textile, food-processing, and grain sectors.

The Soviet authorities also increased the number of local women within the Communist Party. This process was supported by the patriotism, determination, and initiative displayed by many Uzbek women, who believed that socialist ideals corresponded to the interests of the people. By the 1930s, however, an unscientific conclusion was reached that the "women's question" had been resolved. As a result, by a decision of the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks) dated January 5, the women's departments were abolished [5].

Responsibility for work among women was transferred to Commissions for the Improvement of Labor and Living Conditions. In reality, this decision reflected the fact that the Soviet government and the Communist Party had largely achieved their objective of integrating women into social production under the slogan of

“economic liberation.” Women’s labor was widely utilized as a cheap workforce, making them a major productive force within society. At the same time, politically active women increasingly began to demand their rights and express dissatisfaction with the policies pursued by the authoritarian Soviet regime.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Soviet government and the Communist Party used all available administrative methods to involve indigenous women in social and political activities, strengthen party ranks, and secure support for the construction of a “new socialist society.” As a result, the social and political consciousness of Uzbek women increased to a certain extent.

Behind many of these reforms was the hidden objective of maximizing the use of women’s labor. The measures implemented during this period contributed to the emergence of a new generation of women who sought active participation in public life alongside men rather than limiting themselves solely to family responsibilities [6].

In rural areas, women often joined collective farms (kolkhozes) because their husbands offered less resistance under conditions where refusal could lead to exile or property confiscation. At the same time, according to eyewitness accounts, many women saw participation in collective labor as an opportunity to earn their own income and gain financial independence from their husbands [7].

In 1924, only 250 Uzbek women were employed within the handicraft cooperative system. As a result of the “Hujum” campaign, this number increased to 4,258 by 1928. By the mid-1930s, a new cultural and social image of Soviet women had emerged.

Thus, although the Soviet “Hujum” campaign introduced Central Asian women to secular life and contributed to social modernization, it also generated a number of social problems that remain subjects of debate today.

Without doubt, the “Hujum” campaign occupies an important place in the history of Central Asia. Like many other Bolshevik reforms and policies, it is

difficult to evaluate it from only one perspective. On the one hand, it contributed to improving women's social status and quality of life. On the other hand, it created significant social tensions and conflicts within society.

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